

Phra That Phanom Kha Okasa: Cultural Identity Dynamics in A Historical And Changing Context

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 02 ,2025</p> <p>Accepted: April 08,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Kha Okasa of Phra That Phanom, Identity dynamic, Thai-Lao culture, Theravada Buddhism</p>	<p><i>My research aims to study the dynamics of cultural identity amongst the Pra That Phanom Kha Okasa, a group dedicated by rulers and kings to support and uphold Buddhism, in the context of historical and political changes in Laos. The Kha Okasa held the status of servants who were of the lowest social status in the Lao feudal system. When Laos was colonized by the Kingdom of Siam, the role of the Kha Okasa in the culture faded. Under the reign of King Rama V, the central government of Siam ordered to demote the local chief administration in the Lao districts until slavery was abolished. However, despite the changes during that period, the relationship between the Phra That Phanom and Buddhism remained for a long time. Through this relationship, they held on to the meaning of being a Kha Okasa which, for them, was to be a sacred symbol and center of the soul for people across the Mekong River who were dealing with cultural adaptation in the changing world.</i></p>
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Introduction

Kha Okasa (“Khoi Okasa” in local dialect) or Kha pra, are part of a prevalent culture of Kalapana in Theravada Buddhism which was found during the reign of the great King Asoka when he consecrated land and people to Buddhism for worshiping or collecting prestige. The Kha Okasa became like commoners or servants who served the Buddhist religion and took care of monks, temples as well as relics and pagoda. The Kha Okasa were obligated to return the kingdom and serve the country, which meant that they enjoyed certain privileges. This included not being charged tribute (Fine Arts Department, 2008) and the right to not be recruited during war. Being “Kha” is associated with sacred Buddhist symbols that is reflected in the Buddhist culture in relation to the administrative conditions the king has to accumulate his merit. Therefore, the king dedicated his people to serve in Buddhism (such as caring for relics, serve the monks, and be labor in temples). However, when Siam extended their power to rule Lao, the incident affected the Kha Okasa as they were now viewed as a human resource or a citizen that must to pay tribute – an action that was viewed as necessary in economic and political situation at that moment. Thereafter, the Kha Okasa had to pay tribute to their parents as well as look after the relics and serve Buddhism. The Kha Okasa culture then symbolically faded (as perceived by the rulers). Yet, the Kha Okasa tried to maintain their livelihood by expressing their identity and connecting with the Phra That Phanom. In the context of globalization and tourism, the Kha Okasa were used to attract tourism. They integrated their dance posture in the merit festival hosted by the Phra That Phanom and the two groups joined one another to develop the tourism areas that had cultural capital. In the modern age, the meaning of Kha Phra That an Kha Okasa were adjusted to convince general Buddhists who believe in the relics that making wishes or asking children from the relics will help keep the relations with the Phra That Phanom. The Kha Okasa were therefore a dynamic phenomenon and a meaningful composition which should be studied to understand the Buddhist culture in relation to its meaning to people and localities in the different time periods, especially in Theravada Buddhist beliefs in Southeast Asia.

Phra That Phanom and Kha Okasa

Buddhist culture in the Lao kingdom of Lan Xang follows Theravadin Buddhism beliefs which spread into the Lao kingdom of Lan Xang during the significant periods when Buddha came to Sri Kotrabun and predicted the occurrence of the city and the Thapana Chedi which contained the Urangadhatu of the Buddha at the Phu Kam Phra temple, also known as Phra That Phanom (Fine Arts Department, 1994: 66). The Sri Kotrabun is an ancient district which influenced Theravada Buddhism, before the Khmer was influenced in the 12th - 14th centuries, and the local architecture in that area. Around the 19th century, King Fa Ngum brought Theravada Buddhism from Cambodia into his land (Tem Wipakpotchanakit, 1987). King Fa Ngum had tried to change his traditional beliefs by dominating Buddhism with the support from his wife from Khmer however, this was not entirely clearer. Buddhism and traditional beliefs have been adapted and form the foundation in Lao

culture. On the other hand, Buddhist culture had been used to promote power in the government and prestige among the elites. At the same time it was adapted to become a unique characteristic of the Lao society such as the integration with local beliefs and it turned into an important part of society called “Heet 12” (a tradition of making merit in each month of the whole twelve months). The relationship between the Buddhist culture in the Lao kingdom of Lan Xang and the livelihood of the community are related to each other. The temple is a sacred and public space for various social activities as well as a center for cultivating various arts and knowledge in both the secular and moral space. Thus the monks are required to know only know the disciplines, but also be an expert in the arts.

In addition, the main point is the appointment of the monks which gave power to the villagers as they got to choose and appoint the monks whom they believe are called “Hodsong” (Hodsong is based on the social class of the monk i.e. Samret, Sa, Khu, Khu Lakhom, and Khu Yod Keaw) (Boonchuay Srisawat, 1960). In many cases, the monks were flexible and adaptable to participate in seasonal activities and merit-making festivals such as Fireball making, Songkran or help villagers with tasks such as farming (Tem Wipakpotchanakit, 1987; Boonchuay Srisawat, 1960). Nevertheless, the Kha Okasa was a social and cultural status related to Phra That Phanom and was a sacred symbol which was important to the Laos on both sides of the Mekong River for a long time. The Phra That Phanom had a story according to the legend Urangadhathu (Fine Arts Department, 1940) and in the memories of the local people. The legend is about an event which took place around B.E. 8* when the Buddha had a paid visit to the Suvarnabhumi district and sat at Phu Kam Phra to announce that Buddhism predicted the emerging of Marukhakorn city and the prosperity of the city along with stamping the Buddha's footprint as a symbol (the king of Marukhanakorn became a Thapana Chedi Phra That Phanom and covered Ubon Mung Phra Urangkathu later). In the morning of that day, the Buddha returned from his alms giving to the Sri Kotrabun city and stayed at Phu Kam Phra. In the second round of predictions by the Buddha, he predicted that the Phu Kham Pra would be the place for the five Buddhas in Phatharakup, and recalled the Maha Kassapa at that moment. After that, the Maha Kassapa had presented himself in the front of the Buddha immediately and said “Wait Kassapa, Tathagata attained nirvana. You shall bring the Urangadhathu (The Chest relics) placed at the Phu Kam Phra. Please do not ignore Tathagata's commands when the Buddha passed in nirvana. The Maha Kassapa with 500 Buddhist saints brought the Urangkathathu of the Buddha to enshrine it at Phu Kam Pra (Fine Arts Department, 1994). The ruler of city consisted of Praya Suvannapingkan (The chief of Nong Han Luang), Phaya Kham Daeng (The chief of Nong Han Noi), Phaya Chulamanee Phromthat, Phaya Inthaphat Nakorn, and Phaya Nantasen (The chief of Sri Khotboon) and the president of the establishment of Ubon Mung to enshrine the Urangkathathu.

Each Phaya had built and contained various valuables that Ubon Mung had and divided them into 5 areas. They then wished to be a Buddhist saint in the next life, the 500 Buddhist saints who were along side the Maha Kassapa had also rejoined the merit, and then returned to the Ratchapruet district to chant in unison, similar to the five Phayas who also returned to their own city. After that, the chief of Marukhanakorn city and the president of Thapana Chedi Phra That Luang at Phu Kam Pra advised the 5 Buddhist saints and dedicated 3333 Kah Okasa to preserve the Phra That Phanom (Fine Arts Department, 1967). However, in the context of Theravada Buddhism in Southeast Asia, Phra That Phanom became a sacred symbol in the state and were worshipped by the king and general Buddhists. It also turned into a symbol that the chief must take care, restore, and worship consistency since the kingdom of Sri Khotboon and the kingdom of Siam. In kingdom of Lan Xang, the kings had prioritized the Phra That Phanom as a necessary thing that had to be maintained and restored continuously, such as Phra Chao Bodhi Sararat who conducted restoration of Phra That Phanom. Later, in the reign of King Chai Chetthathirat, he dedicated the Kha Okasa to serve the Phra That Phanom and patronized the monks.

When King Suriyawongsa had passed away from the chaos in the palace of Vientiane, the chancellors seized the throne to control the power. A royal dynasty group got into trouble and flocked to ask help from the monks, which they got from Pra Kru Phonsamek who had the discipline and expertise in the arts. Pra Kru Phonsamek took them along with the troops to head down to the Mekong River towards the southern region (Fine Arts Department, 1941). During immigration, the Pra Kru Phonsamek stopped along the river and caused the occurrence in the community on the right-side (now known as Isan or Northeast Thailand) such as Bann Kiew Sam Pan Lam Som Sanook. Due to the immigration from political chaos during this time, the Pra Kru Phonsamek gathered his troops and conducted the additional restoration to Phra That Phanom in the Lan Xang art style. This is an important history of the Phra That Phanom as it was built in the Lan Xang art style

*The numbers of scholars argue that this should take place in B.E.1 as references in Urangkathath Legend, Phra That Pranom Legend, and establishment of another Buddha's relics (Phra That) such as Pra That Lann. In addition, the details in Urangkathathu legend and Phra That Pranom legend reveal that when had completed the Buddha's sacred sanctuary, Phra Maha Kassapa returned for chanting in unison and the chanting in unison should be held in B.E.1 because the tool place after the Buddha was born for 3 months at Satta Bun Kuha cape in Ratchakruet district.

(Kiattisak Bangperng, 2015) before the kingdom of Siam adjusted the Pra That peak in the Field Marshal Pibulsongkram's era.

The Phra That Phanom was therefore considered a sacred symbol of the Buddha and was connected with the legend of the Buddha as well as the sustaining of the monarchy at that time. In local beliefs, Phra That Phanom is a sacred symbol combined with traditional beliefs that reflects the faith of Thai-Lao people on both sides of the Mekong River in the present.

Social Status and Cultural Identity in Political contexts

Who are the Kha Okasa? How are the Kha Okasa related to the culture of Kalpana? Kalpana is a form of religious patronage with the idea of land consecration and labour for religion. It began from Hinduism which was dedicated to worship those who served temples. Later, Mahayana Buddhism also adopted this idea, including Theravada Buddhism when it spread to the local community (Raviwan Phakphot, 1983; Office of the Prime Minister, 1967), especially in elites group for their merit and prestige. Kalpana is aimed to create Satyathithan for great merit in various respects, for example, for Nirvana, the remaining of Buddhism for five thousand years, to be born in Maitreya Buddha era, to devote oneself to the Buddha, and to collect the merit for the good world in the next life or family. These Satyathithan are ideas and beliefs which show a strong belief in Buddhism are reflected in the form of Kalpana (Nichanan Klangwichai, 2017). The elites want to gain merit and as a result they keep fostering Buddhism by dedicating land and slavery for the religion. The Kalpana culture was found throughout all the kingdoms that accepted Theravada Buddhism since the reign of the great Ashoka who customized the role of a king to be a virtuous person and serve Buddhism with built pagodas, dedicated land, and people to nourish Buddhism (Office of the Prime Minister, 1967). The great Ashoka is a virtuous emperor who rules the kingdom with happiness as written in the Suttantapitaka Angutaranikaya Jatukkanibata unit 70, page 86, where it was mentioned that the emperor of the Dharmikha needed to rule the kingdom rightfully, respect the dharma, and hold the Dharma as doctrines of administration which would help the people and kingdom acquire prosperity.

In Buddhism, being the king is not the only rule in the kingdom, but they also have to upbringing Buddhism and be a rightful model to build happiness and prosperity for people. Buddhism is considered as the center of the soul in the kingdom. This belief was passed on to Lanka, a Burmese kingdom, Ayutthaya, Lanna and Lan Xang. For example, in Lanna, around the 17th B.E, the legend of Phra That Lampang Luang claimed that "... she ordered to celebrate the Buddha relics for 7 days and nights and dedicate her land with 5 million cowries to male and female slaves to serve the Buddha relics" (Sanguan Chotisukrat, 1972: 347). Although the Kalpana has the meaning as aforementioned, in some details it might be adjusted with conditions of power structure or administration in the kingdoms. For example, in the Ayutthaya period, the land for the temples and dedicated servants in the west of Songkhla lake was confronted by Malayu pirates, Aceh Aruh pirates, and Hujungkhatana. This conflict had caused drastic damages across the cities and temples. Thus the king provided lands, farms, and servants for monks in the temples. Moreover, the king had promoted the temple and monks to be the center of soul for creating a monastic system like the temples department to counterbalance the monk's power and the local power, and community expansion which made the monks a cultural leader (Raviwan Phakpratt, 1983: 129). Therefore, the Kalpana is dynamic based on the social and political contexts. This point is an important part for researcher to figure out Phra That Phanom as references.

It was assumed that the ancient legends such as Urangadhatu and Kalpana (Kha Okasa) in the Lan Xang culture first appeared when Phaya Sumitthawongsa built a royal pagoda at Phu Kam Phra following the advice of the five Buddhist saints and then dedicated about 3,333 Kha Okasa to serve Phra That Phanom. Later in B.E. 200, the culture is seen to remain in the next reign as well. As appeared in Lao chronicles, the king Phothisararat had paid a visit to worship Phra That Phanom and worship the two siblings of Kha ethnic: Phan Ruen Hin, and Kha Cha Eng to serve Phra That Phanom and bring flowers, incense and candles every year (Thongseub Supamark, 1985). During the reign of king Setthathirath, the king also maintained and conserved the Buddha relics and then dedicated the Kha Okasa to them. In the Lan Xang cultural system, the king is considered as the landlord and god of life (Grant Evans, 2006), but the king is unable to control the entire kingdom by himself, resulting in the distribution of the land to the nobles, and other royal dynasties to establish the chief of district in small areas to be his alter eyes. The monks also had a social status which cannot be underestimated because the monks were considered as the head of villagers and it can be said clearly that the monks had an influence in guiding people through the preaching. In the case of the emerging Pu Mee Boon rebellion (or Pee Boon rebels from the government), it is an example of the reflection of power from local Buddhism which has shaken up the power of the feudal system as it happened quite frequently in Lao culture. Therefore, the temples patronage and serving the monks would create a significant balance between the powers. Giving the people and land to monks was one of the mechanisms to balance the power. This story was recorded by Pastor Marini Romain who rose to evangelize during the reign of Sourigna Vongsa (the King who promoted Buddhism and is known to be one of the most prosperous in the Lan Xang kingdom). He recorded notions about

the power of the monks that “The religious power of the monks at this time might be great”, until the king has to be gentle and maintain the relationship resulting in the king being kind to the monks. Furthermore, he was afraid that if conflict occurred with the monks, they would incite the people to seize his power. If he always strict with the monk’s discipline, they would also try to take revenge on the king. Therefore, he had to protect the monks and say good things to keep the relationship. If there is anyone wants to have luck, be an important person in the kingdom as well as have the king’s power, they must learn from the nobles who served the monks. (Marini Romain, 1999: 65). Marini mentioned the incident where monks made a mistake and the king was the one who considered exoneration, including the knowledge of magic which was owned by the monks who the Lan Xang people believed. This incident further affected the ability of the monk, which ordinary people were not able to do, thus people in Lan Xang believed in themselves and considered monks as privileged people who were highly respected (Marini Romain, 1999: 60-65). In addition, the respect and patronage of the king somehow resulted in the priest being arrogant and boastful and believed in magic to encourage making more merit. In front of the king, they tried to maintain a good relationship, but actually demanded the people to give alms, even the poor, and did not allow and injured person to get healed (other than just using an old piece of cloth to cover the wound). The monks healed the sick for when the king recovered, he would give slaves and land “so, the king dedicated his servants of 1600 persons to serve the monks and the land as a symbol of gratitude” (Marini Romain, 1999: 64). The Khoi or Kha Okasa are considered to have the lowest status in the Lao social hierarchical structure, called traditional feudalism. Originally, land, things, or even people which were dedicated to temples or Buddhism by the king, were considered a treasure of the temple. For those who had to serve the monks without receiving compensation because of their absence in having ownership over the kingdom and when the king dedicated his land for 5,000 years, the successive kings had no authority to revoke ownership (Malinee Klangraphan, 2012). Besides, the Lao society is also an ethnically diverse society. Later, the Thai-Lao ethnicity had power in government system resulting in the Khoi/Kha, where the slave had a relationship with other ethnicities and was counted in the huge group of “Kha” (which means Kha That or slave, Jit Phumisak, 2013). The Kha were herded to be a property of the master and were traded in the market. Khoi Okasa or Kha Okasa therefore, is the person whom the master has dedicated for temple and cannot be called back as labor. The lowest social status in Lao society was hence occupied by the Kha Okasa i.e., peasant, slave, or Kha ethnicity. Even in the reign of King Photsisararath, he paid a visit to worship and restore the Pra That Phanomand dedicated the Kha Okasa and Pan Ruen Hin as the leader instead of the existing Kha Okasa, as the previous generation had faded away. However, the Kha Okasa had a function similar to the ordinary slaves who had to work as a laborer, but they worked for their religion, in farming (which the master dedicated to the temple), to send tribute to the temples, and to look after the temples. The Kha Okasa could not redeem themselves and were independent because they were under the social structure. They just received more privileges than any other slaves as they were not required to be a troop or laborer for the government. As the Lao regulation states, the Kha Okasa cannot ordain as a monk as they have to serve Buddhism. In the early Rattanakosin period, some evidence shows the attitudes from the nobles towards these people that “They must serve in the religion for eternity and across all generations, which was worse than being ordinary slaves. Therefore, they were dedicated to the temples like a herd of cattle who were reproduced over five thousand years” (National Archives of Thailand No. Ror 5 Sor. 8.3/2.4 April Rattanakosin era 125). As mentioned above, the Kha Okasa were a cultural symbol that reflected the faith of Buddhism and the complexity of a hierarchical structure included authorities and negotiation of power between the religion and kingdom.

However, at the beginning of the 24th Buddhist century, the Siamese colonies expanded their power to colonize Lao during the reign of King Thonburi until the beginning of the Rattanakosin period. The colonization had resulted in Laos (Lan Xang) being colonized by Siam, but Siam allowed the administration to follow the traditional system: the 4 main system. The power of government and the tribute collection was under Siam. The objective of dominating the Lao society, politics and culture was to build a Siamese society with a structure that was similar to the Ayutthayan era which was divided into two main classes, namely the ruling class, which consisted of kings, lords, nobles, official staffs and monks, and subordinate class, which consisted of people and slaves. Another group of people who came from the culture of Kalapana had different names such as a) Kha Pra refers to the person who the king dedicated to the temple to serve all activities of the temple and monks, and had to maintain this status eternally (Autit Juengniponsakul, 1985), b) Yom Song refers to the monks who examined meditation and took care of the graduation of theology. The king gave them the privilege of being a laborer in the palace. They were transferred from the Kha Pra department to be Yom Song which is a promotion as the work given was not as difficult such as serving monks who were their relatives (Nittaya Wongviwat, 1981). Lake Wat refers to the Kha Pra and Yom Song whom the king had given at least 25 households or more and “Samana Cruao” which means monks servants. The Lake Wat is completely different for the Kha Pra and Yom Song because they do not belong to the temple and monks but are the royal staff who work in the temple for only three months in a year (Autit Juengniponsakul, 1982). All of a sudden, the Bowring treaty signed with England entailed the shift which gradually turned the country into a capitalist one. The Kha Pra were not an important force for the temples as they were in the past, they only served and maintained the temples and

practiced as monks (Atchara Kanjanomai, 1980). Therefore, the importance of the temple was reduced and at some temples the monks paid government fees instead of recruiting laborers under Siam's social structure. The Kha Okasa continued their roles and duties but as the status of "Lake Wat" who served the monks and the Phra That Phanom for that moment. (Malinee Klangraphan, 2012). The status of Lake Wat was the right of the state and the royal staff which the king dedicated to the monks (It showed a significant view that the Kha Okasa do not define themselves as Kha Pra over whom only the temple can have full authority to handle the government authority). The Kha Okasa who used to serve the Phra That Phanom since Lan Xang era, when under Siamese rule, they were migrated to be under the Siamese state which resulted in the meaning of Kha Okasa becoming "Lake Wat," - the person who had to work for religion and the state at the same time, which meant that the government can re-call them as well. With these reasons the local chief in Nakhon Phanom and Mukda usually seized the Lake Wat for tribute and being laborers as well as being their own slave. As a result, this story was prosecuted to the central government in Bangkok. This implied that when political power changed (from Lan Xang to Siam) the meaning and status of the Kha Okasa also changed with the context. The story of the Lake Wat in Phra That Phanom to collect tribute and labor took place because Phra That Phanom was located between Nakhon Phanom and Mukdahan province. Then the local chief of Nakhon Phanom and Mukdahan tried to expand their power to control and collect tributes and laborers. This resulted in the Thao Pia and Lake Wat in Phra That Phanom going to Bangkok and they were the two local chiefs who were oppressed and used. The central government from Bangkok hence appointed Phra Sri Song Fa as Phra Pitak Chedi, Nai Kong Tua Lek, and Kha Okasa of Phra That Phanom to be under the administration of central government in Bangkok only. The rest of Kha Okasa who volunteered to work in the city, His Majesty King Chulalongkorn gave the authorities to the local chiefs of Mukdahan, Nakhon Phanom, and Sakon Nakhon province to control and collect tribute to to send Bangkok.

Later, Chao Phaya Pasakornwong had asked Kha Pra, Yom Song, and Lake Wat to return to the central government and change the money to maintain the temples, but were opposed by Krom Muen Prajaksillapakhom. King Chulalongkorn did not agree because the administrative units had to lose their benefits, therefore, Krom Muen Prajaksillapakhom proposed a solution by controlling and expediting the collection of money. In this period, Kha Pra, Yom Song, and Lake Wat had begun to undergo another major change because instead of working for the temples, they had to pay wages instead. In 1945 (the reign of king Rama V), the Conscriptio act was enacted to officialise abolition of slavery in Thailand resulting in the Kha Pra, Som Song, and Lake Wat becoming soldiers along with the occurrence of the French colonies, to take acquisition over the Mekong River on the left-side. King Chulalongkorn therefore accelerated the improvement of the local government around the Isan district, or the right-side of the Mekong River, to be more concise and issued the announcement to not allow the Thao Khun to force Chao, Thao, Khun and the people who set up houses on the east side to cross over to the right side. It can be said that the Kha Okasa (both the social status and the cultural identity) were abolished to be people just like other ethnicities in Siam. It can be noticed that the expansion of Siam entailed relations between Buddhism and culture which had overlapped in both the state and local government. The Kha Okasa is likely to be brought under the Buddhist culture in the name of "Lake Wat" and devalued the meaning and the privilege of the social status since the Lan Xang kingdom and became a citizen who were not different from slaves and had to pay tribute to their governments. When the government benefited from these people, they had tried to take control of them as soldiers and laborers until it caused conflict between the local chiefs who had taken these people under their own power. In this incident, the Kha Okasa or Lake Wat of Phra That Phanom had negotiated with a complaint to the central government in Bangkok resulting in the central government of Bangkok taking the complaint under their responsibility. However, in the reign of King Rama V, the Kha Okasa had encountered with the changes once again when the king enacted the slavery abolishment policy which in turn affected the Kha Okasa status which faded away from Thai social and cultural identity. However, the long relationship with the Phra That Phanom had formed the faith of the Kha Okasa as they tried to negotiate to maintain the social status as in the past even if it was not successful in the age of reformation and transformation under the northeastern local government. Especially, in the reign of King Rama V when the government, economy and society had changes and caused the conditions and negotiations to reconstruct the cultural identity. The Kha Okasa had applied their cultural resources as historical memories and cultural names which reflected their relationship with the Phra That Phanom in the meaning "Kha Okasa Phra That Phanom" to create an identity with conditions such as tourism which will be discussed in the next part.

Cultural Identity Dynamic under the Changes

The relationship with Phra That Phanom which has been there for a long time, resulted in the realization of being the Kha Okasa. For the people who call themselves Kha Okasa through symbols such as the name, the reproduction of the legend or the history of being Kha Okasa reproduced, interpreted, and constructed identities. In political, societal, and economical changes, the Kha Okasa tried to show their cultural identity not just as a symbolic identity, but also as related to the importance of Phra That Phanom as a role in the faith and

livelihood of the local people. In other words, the Phra That Phanom had an important role as representatives of the Buddhist belief at both local and regional levels. Cultural identity related to the history of Phra That Phanom or linked Phra That Phanom with their own cultural characteristics affected the Kha Okasa who had value and importance as well. According to the traditional culture of Kha Okasa, when the harvesting season arrived, every Kha Okasa had to bring rice, crops, cereals, Prasat Phueng, and sacrifice things to the relics. This action is called “SiaKhaHua Ritual” and is considered to be an important tradition for Kha Okasa. It is also called the “Kao Bichabthagaya Offering” which is an important cultural resource for the Kha Okasa. However, Thailand has been promoting tourism since the end of B.E. 2500 (Sudaen Wisuthilak, 2013: 7) and promotes tourism as a tool for national development till today (Bunyasarit Anek). Suk, 2015: 10-11). The tourism policy therefore had a strong local influence, especially cultural tourism (Kiattisak Bangperng, 2015). In this context, Phra That Phanom, which was the identity of the Isan local culture, had turned out to be an important symbol of the cultural value to promote tourism. For this reason, the annual merit festival of Phra That Phanom on the 15th waxing moon of the 3rd month (called the Third-month Merit festival (Boon Deun Sam) or the worship of Phra That Phanom), which was held to worship Phra That Phanom had the purpose of tourism. The Kha Okasa had brought the tradition of “Kao Bichabthagaya Offering” to invent, create, and express the identity of being the Kha Okasa in Phra That Phanom along with inventing the Phra That Phanom dance to show good art and culture in tourism. Since the past, the Phra That Phanom worshipping festival in the third month has been an ancient festival in the community. It is a procession of Phra Uppakut from the Mekong River to worship in the Kha Okasa communities around Phra That Phanom which is led by the president of Phra That Phanom Tum Hom Pattana Mueang group (Thanatchai Khampong, 2020: Interview). He said that this festival might be held during the reign of Phra Kru Viroj Rattanabol who restored Phra That Phanom in 1907s.[†]The annual festival which was as an “invented culture” added the show of welcoming guests. King Rama IX had paid a visit to the Phra That Phanom in 1955 and the Kha Okasa got the opportunity to create a beautiful dance to present in front of the throne (Phichet Saipan, 2016). During this event, the Kha Okasa of Phra That Phanom got the opportunity to express their dance to the others as a tool to show their identity of being a Phra That Phanom and the meaning and value that jointly created the community. After that the dances were presented by various groups of women and various styles thus becoming a significant element to worship the Phra That Phanom as well as on important occasions when organizing other activities related to Phra That Phanom and even more concentrated in the context of the present tourism in Thai society in aspects of cultural, economic, and national development.

In the context of tourism, the Nakhon Phanom Provincial Government Office has established a tourism promotion policy for 8 tribes that exist in the province and put up Phra That Phanom as an important symbol of the province. There is a metaphor for saying that the “Phra That Phanom are like a living room of the Nakhon Phanom Province” (Anantachai Khampong, 2020: Interview) which relates to the meaning of tourism, culture and religion. An obvious phenomenon in the area of tourism is worshipping the relics of the birthplace (7 days) with Phra That Phanom as the main focus. This phenomenon has also made tourism influence the Phra That Phanom and Kha Okasa. The Kha Okasa around Phra That Phanom have brought material resources, culture, traditions, and the way of life to create tourist materials and establish the “Kha Okasa group of Phra That Phanom Tumhome Pattana ” which play a role in tourism development in the area around Phra That Phanom: 1) restoration of ancient houses in colonial style architecture which were built in the past since the French colonial era has influenced Laos and the Phra That Phanom district around the beginning of the 25th century. The architectures had brought to be shown as ancient cultural objects such as household appliances and a hotel accommodation for tourists, 2) organizing organic agriculture along the Mekong River by simulating the way of life in relation to the past life of the Kha Okasa for tourists, 3) a walking street and trade shows, community products and the Kha Okasa dance and 4) local culture preservation by adopting the Kha Okasa musical instrument which had been provided by the Royal Musical Instrument from the Lan Xang Kingdom (Chao Anuwong) and then have a follow-up in the Kham Pom family to show the tourist around. The Kha Okasa of Phra That Phanom adopted the 12-month tradition (Heet 12) organized by the Isan to invent a tourism culture that allowed the Kha Okasa to show their culture (to welcome tourists) every month of the year. In March, they organized a dance to worship the Phra That Phanom on the first and last Saturday of the month, in April, they had a tradition of sending water to Phra That Phanom and in May, they organized a ceremony for the Hor Chao Huen Sam Pra Aong and Thet Maha Chat.

This phenomenon reflected the adaptation to socio-cultural changes to express cultural identity in tourism which invented, created, and interpreted a new culture for tourism. For example, the Kao Bichabthagaya Offering had been interpreted from the SiaKhaHua Ritual in which they did not have to be charged tribute (in

[†] Later, this tradition became a ritual in the Kha Okasa community around Phra That Phanom and Laos around Mekong River to pay respect and turned into a memory and faith about “When was born in a lifetime, if should pay respect to Phra That Phanom at once in the third month” (Mong Apaiso, 2020: Interview), which will bring a great of merit to the next life.

the past) to make merit to worship Phra That Phanom, both which are the merit-making of relics and a cultural show for tourism about the traditional Buddhism culture in a modern age. From field study in Phra That Phanom, villagers descended from the Kha Okasa to worship in Phra That Phanom festival, “The Kha Okasa have to come and dance to worship the relics which is considered as an important part of merit-making” (Yuenyong Phonrat, 2020: Interview).

In addition, it can be noticed that the Kha Okasa had faded with the change of government, but the Kha Okasa community (Around Phra That Phanom temple) maintained the story of “being descendants from the Kha Okasa of Phra That Phanom” (Kasemsak Paripunno, 2020: Interview). Some people claim that “they are descendants from the Kha Okasa of Phra That Phanom and rely on the temples to sell souvenirs so that tourists pay respect to the Phra That Phanom for prosperity. All communities around Phra That Phanom are the Kha Okasa of Phra That Phanom and descendants of Phra That ”(Mong Apaiso, 2020: Interview). However, the interpretation of the “Kha Okasa” to “the descendants of Phra That” means that the relationship of the Phra That Phanom is a sacred object which influences daily life in the community, hence they are the descendants of Phra That Phanom and have become a sacred symbol that protects their lives. In the context of changes, the “Kha Okasa” has transformed into a symbolic explanation of being “the descendants of Phra That Phanom” and has resulted in the local people or Buddhists being able to refer to themselves with the flexibility of this meaning. In general, Buddhists can describe themselves as the descendants of Phra That Phanom as well as through a ritual called “Tang Khan Ha” in order to be the descendent of Phra That Phanom. The group of Buddhists also revered Phra That Phanom as a sacred object that could bless their children (This sacred feature is widely known among Buddhists who respect Phra That Phanom). Children who are born will have a relationship as a child of Phra That Phanom. With the interpretation of the community, it allowed outsiders to use the meaning of being Kha Okasa or the descendent of Phra That Phanom (among the Buddhists who respect Phra That Phanom) which was widely spread throughout both local and inter-regional areas. The related research about Kalpana or Kha Okasa aims to define the meaning, historical development, role and importance of the Buddhist culture (Tosapon Athan, 1999; Raviwan Phakprot, 1983; Malinee Klangpraphan, 2012) as well as cultural characteristics and social networks (Nichanan Klangwichai, 2017) linked to Buddhist culture. However, when the notion of racial and ethnic characteristics of the Kha Okasa came about, it was found that they did not have a racial or ethnic identity. In the essentialism of ethnography (which is currently debates) the existence of the Kha Okasa only arises in the social status, in terms of the relationship between the kingdom and the religion by being dedicated or entrusted to being a Buddhist servant. Originally, the Kha Okasa is existed in terms of social status but now, the meaning is dependent on political, governmental and economic changes. Therefore, the status and identity of the Kha Okasa has become a cultural history which evolved into an “imaginary memory” and is applied in the present through the integration of tourism.

The researcher noticed that the Kha Okasa of Phra That Phanom in the Lan Xang culture has faded away in aspects of the traditional meaning as a social status, but it continued to interpret and reproduce the existence of the Kha Okasa through memory and historical imagination based on interacted conditions such as tourism and invented history. Thus, understanding the cultural practices behind their identity through explanations and interpretations of new meanings may benefit cultural practices in negotiations, interpretations, and cultural adaptation according to conditions and situations under the Buddhist culture.

Conclusion

The Kha Okasa are a group of people who were dedicated to serve as monks and Buddhism without the originally innate relationship, but rather to be a social status which built on the relationship between the religion and the kingdom. The Kha Okasa is a culture of Kalpana which is widely found in the Buddhist states of Southeast Asia as a form of religious patronage with the idea of land consecration and as laborers of the religion. It can be assumed that the culture was influenced by Hindu tradition which offered people or slaves and opportunity to serve the temples. In the study of the Kha Okasa of Phra That Phanom in the context of Lao culture, it not only showed the meaning of the common culture in the Kalpana but also reflected the complexity of a hierarchical social structure known as a feudal system in which the Kha Okasa were at the lowest class (Kha Khoi) of the traditional Lao social structure. Thus, they were the first group to be irreversibly dedicated to the temple with full authority from the temples. It also reflected the power of the elite and the relationship with the religion in a patronage. The religion was supported to uphold the power and righteousness in the administration while the Kha Okasa were one of the mechanisms to patronize the monks and Buddhism. In the early 24th Buddhist century, the local colonies of Siam had expanded their power to rule the Lao kingdom resulting in Lan Xang being colonized under the social structure of Siam. The Kha Okasa of Phra That Phanom changed the status to “Lake Wat” giving them a half citizen status and they were made to serve monks and Buddhism at the same time (they were also asked to pay tribute to the state which caused the governor to try and take them as laborers to pay tribute until the central government in Bangkok took them under their responsibility) Therefore, the meaning of Kha Okasa deteriorated and faded away in the reign of King Rama V

when he abolished the slavery policy. However, the long relationship with the Phra That Phanom had formed the faith of the Kha Okasawich was embedded in their culture along with the symbolic status in local areas around Phra That Phanom which was continued consistently. Furthermore, the changes in politics, the economy, and the society resulted in the condition and space for negotiation to reconstruct the cultural identity in tourism.

Therefore, the Kha Okasa used their cultural resources such as historical memories, cultural names and the descendants of an imaginary ancestor which aimed to reflect the identity related to Phra That Phanom in the meaning “Kha Okasa Phra That Phanom” to build a tourist identity. This allowed them to place their self-importance status in the annual merit-making festival of Phra That Phanom through the invention of traditional dances where they worshipped the sacred relics for the tourists to perceive the cultural characteristics and belonging to the Phra That Phanom. Additionally, they organized groups to organize “the Kha Okasa group of Phra That Phanom Tumhome Pattana” to develop areas, cultural objects, traditions, and ways of life that corresponded with the current tourist trends and the tourism promotion policy by the government in Phra That Phanom. The Kha Okasa is therefore an agency that shows dynamic identity in historical and changes contexts. Phenomena about the Kha Okasa in this article reflects the Buddhist culture which was adapted to the values, local culture, and ideology. Especially the politics and government of the central government in Southeast Asia which caused the power relationship and social status completion. The Kha Okasa were a group of slaves and they were considered to be at the lowest level of the social structure in the Theravada Buddhism in the Lan Xang and Siamese Kingdom. They dynamically followed a power relationship and changed until they formed a consciousness and developed into action about which power to adapt and took advantage in each situation. Therefore, the view of Theravada Buddhism is based on principles in the doctrine and principles of karma which reflects individuality and equality. The individuality is subject to karma: those who do karma will receive the results of that karma. There is no producer or support. In this case, the Kha Okasa under the Buddhist culture and doctrines may have to be interpreted and reconsidered in terms of politics and transformation, and particularly adapt to the local society, culture, and ideology.

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